

Tool 19 Long-term engagement

Welcome to the Citizen Science Starter Kit.

This template is part of Module 4 “Getting started with citizen science” (phase 3 – launch) and will help you to reflect on how to foster continued engagement by your participants.

Please download this template to your own folder and fill it in on your local computer. If you have any further questions about this template, please contact citizenscience@vub.be.

Fill out the empty fields below, based on Rotman et al. (2012)¹, to reflect on how your citizen science project can tap into different motives for long-term participation. The keywords in *italics* can serve as a starting point and will be useful to incorporate or take into account.

Continued motives	Motive	What does the project offer participants with regard to this motive?
	Trust (keywords: <i>skills, value, time, leadership roles</i>)	
	Common goals (keywords: <i>communication, structured protocols, updates</i>)	

¹ Rotman, D., Preece, J., Hammock, J., Procita, K., Hansen, D., Parr, C., ... & Jacobs, D. (2012, February). Dynamic changes in motivation in collaborative citizen-science projects. In *Proceedings of the ACM 2012 conference on computer supported cooperative work* (pp. 217-226).

	Acknowledgement (keywords: <i>recognition, attribution, value</i>)	
	Mentorship (keywords: <i>training, empowerment, closeness</i>)	

An additional checklist that might prove useful is to reflect on **possible barriers** to (initial or continued) participation. We compiled the following table from different studies². Go over each of the potential barriers on it and consider which one(s) might pose an issue in your project.

Barrier	Timing (initial or continued)
Technical limitations of (data collection) app	Initial
Inaccessible language	Initial
Lack of awareness raising	Initial
Required time commitment of the citizen scientist	Continued
Technology availability and usability	Continued
Lack of attention towards training and feedback	Continued
Complex/burdensome online reporting systems	Continued
Complex communication	Continued
Difficult data contribution process	Continued
Unclear how contributions added to outcome/impact	Continued
Excessive feeling of competition (with other citizen scientists)	Continued
Limited engagement between organizers and citizen scientists	Continued

²The table was developed for the deliverable “D6.1 Engagement strategy for HackAIR community involvement” of the H2020 project HackAIR and can be found p.23.

Limited feedback on quality of data	Continued
Limited information on the project/campaign	Continued
Limited communication of outcomes	Continued
Lack of awareness/understanding about correct sensor use	Continued